

Deep water

Deepwater rice yields in Bangladesh

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A severe drought from April to early June 1979 caused poor seedling stands and delayed sowing on the lower Ganges floodplain. Flooding in July damaged the late-planted broadcast aman (b. aman or deepwater rice) crop. Except for the later flood inundation and recession, the 1979 flooding pattern was similar to that of 1978.

The overall mean yield for 101 crop-cuts in 1979 was 2.1 t/ha (range, 0.6–3.7t/ha), 2% higher than farmers' estimates. The mean yield on the Meghna floodplain was significantly higher than that on the Lower Ganges and Lower Jamuna floodplains.

Thirty-three varieties were sampled, eight of them for the first time. The varieties were largely zone-specific and strongly photoperiod sensitive; the mean yields of 6 exceeded 2.5 t/ha. The highest yields were associated with water depths of 1.2 to 1.8 m; late-maturing varieties yielded less than medium- and early-maturing varieties.

Two-thirds of the fields were pure stands of b. aman, a fourth were mixed with aus, and only 6% were mixed with other crops (millet, sesame, chili); three fields were planted to deepwater rice after boro. Yields of b. aman were 25% higher in pure stands but mixed aus – b. aman stands outyielded pure stands in total grain by 0.5 t/ha. Fertilizer was applied to 31% of the pure stands and 30% of the mixed stands, and was used most frequently on the Meghna floodplain. It increased yields in pure stands by 14%.

The ear-cutting caterpillar and ufra nematode caused little damage in the

The ten highest yielding broadcast aman varieties in 1977, 1978, and 1979. Bangladesh.

Variety	Samples (no.)	Mean ^a yield (t/ha)	Frequency ≥ 3 t/ha (%)	Floodplain
Gila Mite	4	3.0	25	Meghna
Pankaish	13	2.8	31	Meghna
Khama	16	2.6	31	Meghna
Kartik Sail	9	2.6	33	Meghna
Chota Bawalia	15	2.5	13	Jamuna
Sarsari	24	2.5	25	Ganges
Bawalia	7	2.5	29	Jamuna
Lakshmi Digha	17	2.4	6	Ganges
Digha	10	2.3	10	Jamuna
Hijal Digha	6	2.3	0	Jamuna

^aAnalysis of variance was nonsignificant.

areas sampled. Whiteheads, caused mainly by stem borers, increased in 1979 to 5.4% (101 counts), but early stem damage was lower than in 1978. Rat activity was severe, especially on the Meghna floodplain; 13% of the fields suffered serious grain loss at harvest. Mealy bugs, encouraged by the early drought, caused damage on all floodplains.

Yields in 1979 were 11% lower than in 1978; the largest decline, 0.4 t/ha, was in the Ganges floodplain. Farmers reported total crop loss on 3% of their field. These mean yields are still almost double those quoted in government statistics.

Comparing 1979 and 1978 data at 12 common sites with 21 common

varieties, there was little change in the proportion of mixed aus - b. aman cropping, fertilizer use, and weeding intensity; from 88 to 89% of the fields were double- or triple-cropped. The 1979 drought reduced the amount of mixed nonrice cropping, especially on the Ganges floodplain, and delayed sowing of b. aman on the Jamuna and Ganges floodplains.

In 3 years of crop-cut sampling (1977–1979), 45 b. aman varieties were used. Yields exceeded 3.5 t/ha for 7 varieties; the 6 top varieties – Gila Mite, Pankaish, Khama, Kartik Sail, Chota Bawalia, Sarsari – averaged more than 2.5 t/ha, and yielded more than 3 t/ha in 25% of the fields sampled (see table). ■

Performance and head rice yields of genotypes under flash flood and waterlogged conditions

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Twenty-six cultivars of long growth duration developed at Chinsurah were tested under typical rainfed wetland conditions in a replicated yield trial in 1978 kharif.

The water depth during most of the crop-growth period exceeded 50 cm (see figure). Water depth was maximum –

125 cm – during the September flood at 135 days after transplanting; the semidwarf lines remained fully submerged for 1 week.

Despite floods at the end of the vegetative phase, 4 tall indicas – Kumargore, OC1393, Patnai 23, and NC1281 – and 2 intermediate Chinsurah lines – CN603 and CNM539 – yielded from 2.5 to 3.6 t/ha (see table). Pankaj yielded only 1 t/ha.

Head rice (husk removed) is the ultimate product of grain yield. The 7 lines differed considerably in husk content. The husk content was 13% for CN603 and 21% for Kumargore, a tall

Water depth (cm)

Water depth during the crop-growth period at the Chinsurah Rice Research Station, West Bengal, India, 1978.

Yield, grain characteristics, and field tolerance for stem borers of some wetland rice cultures. Chinsurah, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Grain wt loss (%) due to husk removal	Estimated kernel yield (t/ha)	100-grain wt (g)		Stem borer damage ^b
				Rough rice	Head rice	
Kumargore	3.6	21	2.8	3.2	2.5	1
OC1393	3.0	20	2.4	3.0	2.4	3
NC1281	2.5	27	1.8	2.4	1.8	3
Patnai 23	2.5	18	2.1	3.0	2.5	3
CNM539	2.5	27	1.8	1.8	1.3	3
CN603	2.5	13	2.1	3.1	2.7	3
Pankaj (check)	1.0	19	0.8	2.5	2.0	5
C.D. (5%)	1.0		0.7			

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b At 40 days after transplanting; 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible, and 9 = highly susceptible.

indica. Although the bold-grained Kumargore had a high rough rice yield, its kernel yield after husk removal was reduced to 2.8 t/ha. Based on kernel yield, Kumargore was statistically similar to OC1393 and CN603, and superior to other entries.

CN603 is of intermediate height with more culm stiffness than most tall indicas.

It has long slender grains with white kernels. Most traditional indica cultivars in West Bengal have bold, red kernels.

In addition to flood submergence and water stagnation the trial was subjected to severe stem borer incidence at early tillering. Kumargore was tolerant of stem borers; CN603 and CNM539 were moderately tolerant. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Cold tolerance

Selection for cold tolerance at seedling stage during rapid generation advance

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During the rapid generation advance (RGA) of breeding materials for low temperature areas, screening for cold

tolerance at different growth stages may be desirable. The easiest stage to screen is at seedling stage when bulk materials can be easily handled and very little space is needed. The possibility of screening for cold tolerance at the seedling stage during RGA was tested. A preliminary trial used a susceptible cultivar, IR8 (a semidwarf indica), and a cold-tolerant

cultivar, Fujisaka 5 (a japonica). Screening for cold water tolerance at the seedling stage involved germinating the seeds in pots and subjecting the 10-day-old seedlings to 12°C water for 10 days, IR8 turned brown, but Fujisaka 5 remained green. However, such treatment delayed flowering by 7 days in Fujisaka 5 and by as much as 22 days in IR8 (Table 1), and partially defeated the purpose of the RGA in shortening the life cycle, especially in IR8.

The possibility of screening for cold tolerance at the seedling stage of segregating F₃, materials with a consequent delay in heading date was studied using the crosses IR20654 (K78-13/IR5908-125-1) and IR22553 (Fujisaka 5/Kn1B-361-1-8-6-9).

The seeds were sown in plastic pots (46 x 46 mm top, 36 x 36 mm bottom) filled with soil and added fertilizer. Ten days after sowing, the plants were subjected to 12°C cold water for 10 days. The plants were scored for leaf yellowing: a score of 1 was best, and 9 indicated almost dead or dead plants. Each F₃ line had a corresponding untreated plant, which was grown to maturity, and the flowering dates of both sets were noted.

A number of F₃ plants (4% in IR22553 and 14% in IR20654) had scores of 1 to 3. Removal of the susceptible lines (score 7 to 9) eliminated 87 and 58% of the F₃, plants in the two crosses studied and increased the available greenhouse space for use within 30 days after sowing.

The results show that cold water treatment at the seedling stage generally delayed the heading date of the two

Table 1. Growth duration of 2 rice varieties subjected to low water temperature at seedling stage. IRRI, 1980.

Variety	Growth (days)		Cold tolerance score ^a
	Treated plants	Untreated plants	
Fujisaka 5	52*	45	1.2
IR8	102*	80	7.7

*Significant at .05 level. ^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = Plants have natural color and normal rate of growth and flowering. 9 = Plants stunted with yellow to brown leaves and much delayed in development and poor panicle exertion.